

Density functional theory calculations for the enhanced quantum capacitance of chemically modified graphene nano-ribbon supercapacitor electrodes.

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Abstract

Graphene-based materials have been proposed as promising electrodes for super capacitors. Recently, it has been found that one of the limitations of graphene electrodes is the finite quantum capacitance. In this work, we investigate the impact of adatom adsorption or functionalization of graphene on the electronic structure and quantum capacitance. Density functional theory calculations were performed to simulate the electronic structure and the quantum capacitance variation with different adatom concentration. Chemical modifications with various width terminations of graphene nanoribbon are tried to enhance the quantum capacitance. We compared the quantum capacitance of graphene with different concentrations of oxygen on all possible positions. Our results clearly show that the number of oxygen containing groups and the location of oxide region largely influence the electronic properties of graphene nanoribbon and thus the quantum capacitance when compared to pristine graphene. Our work highlights the importance of the quantum capacitance in the overall performance of graphene-based super capacitors.

Graphene Nanoribbon , Chemical modification of GNR , Quantum capacitance.

References

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